

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF DAMAGE PROPAGATION IN OVERHEIGHT COMPACT TENSION TESTS

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SUMMARY

At the component level composites failure involves complex interaction of damage modes. Here a finite element approach which explicitly models the sub-critical damage was used to predict the failure of specimens designed to simulate damage in large scale components. Load vs. disp., delamination, fibre failure and surface failure are all well predicted.

Keywords: finite element method, delamination, splitting, fibre breakage

INTRODUCTION

The Overheight Compact Tension (OCT) specimen has been designed to characterise the damage process in large composite structures. In particular it allows for stable crack propagation ahead of the initial machined notch. Previous work on OCT tests has characterized typical load vs. pin opening displacement (POD) curves for a range of IM7/8552 carbon-epoxy laminates with different lay-ups [1]. Delamination in these specimens from tests interrupted at various load levels prior to ultimate failure was detected through C-scans. In this work, a finite element modelling approach which explicitly models the splitting, delamination and fibre failure was used to simulate the sub-critical damage interaction and damage propagation in OCT tests. Cohesive interface elements with mixed mode failure criteria [2] are used to model splitting and delamination within and between plies and a Weibull statistical failure criterion is implemented within the ply solid elements to simulate the fibre failure. This approach is based on the following assumptions:

1. A multi-directional composite laminate consists of a number of laminae with different orientations connected by matrix which can be modeled using cohesive elements. The influence of one lamina on another in a laminate model is realized by the cohesive elements between them.
2. The role of cohesive elements between plies is to transfer the load from one lamina to another and predict delamination failure. The existence of cohesive elements does not influence the material properties of a lamina on its own.
3. Fibre failure in a laminate is brittle. The probability of fibre tensile failure in a laminate is only influenced by the flaw distribution and longitudinal tensile stress. The

influence of transverse in-plane stress, out-of-plane stress and shear stresses on the fibre tensile failure probability can be neglected.

4. In a finite zone where one constant stress solid element is applied in the model of a laminate, the material is orthotropic elastic before fibre failure happens. The tensile stress is considered as being uniformly distributed through the element volume. A single point integration is used for updating stresses. The tensile survival probability of this zone follows the simple two-parameter Weibull model [3]:

$$S_i(\sigma) = \exp\left(-V_i\left(\frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_o}\right)^m\right) \quad (1)$$

Where σ_o is the characteristic strength (or scale parameter) and m is the Weibull modulus (or shape parameter). σ_i and V_i are elemental longitudinal tensile stress and volume respectively. The survival probability of the whole laminate would be:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{lamin ate}(\sigma) &= \prod_{i=1}^{TotalNoofSolidElements} S_i(\sigma) = \prod_{i=1}^{TotalNoofSolidElements} \left(\exp\left(-V_i\left(\frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_o}\right)^m\right) \right) \\ &= \exp\left(\sum_{i=1}^{TotalNoofSolidElements} -V_i\left(\frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_o}\right)^m\right) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Using the assumption of the equal probability of survival at the failure load for the fibres in a laminate and in a unit volume material, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{lamin ate}(\sigma) &= S_{unit}(\sigma) \Rightarrow \\ \exp\left(\sum_{i=1}^{TotalNoofSolidElements} -V_i\left(\frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_o}\right)^m\right) &= \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\sigma_{unit}}{\sigma_o}\right)^m\right) \Rightarrow \\ \sum_{i=1}^{TotalNoofSolidElements} V_i\left(\frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_{unit}}\right)^m &= 1 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where σ_{unit} is the unidirectional failure strength of a unit volume material.

When the probability of survival of in a laminate satisfies the following equation (4), tensile failure of the fibres occurs within the laminate.

$$\begin{aligned} S_{lamin ate}(\sigma) &\leq S_{unit}(\sigma) \Rightarrow \\ \exp\left(\sum_{i=1}^{TotalNoofSolidElements} -V_i\left(\frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_o}\right)^m\right) &\leq \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\sigma_{unit}}{\sigma_o}\right)^m\right) \Rightarrow \\ \sum_{i=1}^{TotalNoofSolidElements} V_i\left(\frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_{unit}}\right)^m &\geq 1 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

5. Unlike the weakest-link theory [4] or other parallel [5] and sequential multi-step failure models [6] which usually assume that the whole specimen or lamina fails after

the critical failure probability is satisfied, it is assumed in this work that only the elements with the maximum longitudinal tensile stress fail when the equation (4) is satisfied. The failed elements are removed from the laminate model and the load is automatically redistributed to other remaining elements by the FEA program. With the load continuing, stresses keep accumulating in fibres till the equation (4) is satisfied again, then further elements with the maximum longitudinal tensile stresses are removed. In this way, the fibre failure in a laminate is progressive and arbitrary configurations of fibre breaks are analyzed without use of idealized load sharing rules.

Models for different lay-ups use the same material properties and Weibull parameters in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1 Fibre material properties of IM7/8552

0° Tensile Modulus (GPa)	90° Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Characteristic strength σ_o (MPa)	Weibull modulus m
161	11.4	3131	41

Table 2. Cohesive material properties of IM7/8552

Mode I Fracture Energy G_{IC} (N/mm)	Mode II Fracture Energy G_{IIC} (N/mm)	Mode I Yield Stress (MPa)	Mode II Yield Stress (MPa)
0.2	1.0	60	90

MODEL SETUP

Model Control

All models were run in the explicit finite element code LS-Dyna. Due to symmetry of the layup, all models used half models through the thickness as shown in Figure 1. A thermal load with temperature decreasing from 180° C to 20° C was applied to each model first, then a prescribed motion with rate of 200mm/s was applied at each of the holes of the models until the Pin Opening Displacement (POD) reached 3.8mm or more. The higher than experimental loading rate is necessary in the model to achieve reasonable simulation times but monitored to ensure excessive dynamic effects are not introduced.

A global damping factor of 1.0 was applied in the models. Type 5 hourglass control was used (Flanagan-Belytschko stiffness form with exact volume integration for solid elements) with a co-efficient of 0.1 (default value). The default values of 1.5 and 0.06

were used for the quadratic and linear bulk viscosity coefficients respectively. A parametric study on the influence of these values showed that damping factor between 0.1 and 3.0, hourglass control coefficient between 0.01 and 0.1, quadratic bulk viscosity coefficient between 1.0 and 1.5 and linear bulk viscosity coefficient between 0.01 and 0.06 would have very small influence on the simulation results.

Figure 1 Load and boundary conditions of the specimen

Mesh in Thickness Direction

Each individual ply was modeled with one solid element in the thickness direction. Eight different layups were considered, four cross-ply and four quasi-isotropic. For each of the cross-ply and quasi-isotropic layups there were 2 and 4mm thick laminates. Each thickness for each layup included a blocked ply and dispersed ply variant. The total number of elements in the thickness direction for different lay-ups are shown in Table 3. Cohesive elements were put between plies to simulate the delamination within a laminate.

Table 3 Number of elements in thickness direction for different lay-ups

Layup (dispersed ply)	Number of elements in thickness direction	Layup (blocked ply)	Number of elements in thickness direction
$[0/90]_{4s}$	8	$[0_2/90_2]_{2s}$	4
$[0/90]_{8s}$	16	$[0_4/90_4]_{2s}$	4
$[45/90/-45/0]_{2s}$	8	$[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_s$	4
$[45/90/-45/0]_{4s}$	16	$[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_s$	4

In-plane Mesh

In the 45° and -45° plies, there are 6 potential splits modeled from the edge of the notch with 0.5mm offset. These are included through lines of coincident nodes joined by the cohesive interface elements. In the 90° plies, there are 2 splits. In the 0° plies, there is 1 split before the notch tip, 1 split right through the notch tip and 24 splits after the notch tip. Details of the potential splits in different plies are shown in Figure 2. This particular arrangement of splits in various plies refers to X-ray images of specimens, in which intra-ply splitting can be clearly distinguished. A study about the influence of splits showed that the splits right through the notch largely affected the initial failure of specimens and splits off the notch affected the failure propagation in specimens.

Figure 2 Details of splits put within plies

MODEL RESULTS

The numerical simulation is summarized in three aspects: Load vs. POD curves, delamination and surface failure appearance. These results are compared with experimental results for the different lay-ups as the follows:

1. Results of blocked ply $[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_s$ (4mm) laminates

The Load vs. POD curve, delamination and surface failure of this lay-up are respectively shown in Figures 3, 4 and 5. In figure 4 the numerical delamination pattern is shown by the individual failed interface elements in red at all interlaminar interfaces superimposed. The intra-ply splits within all plies (superimposed) are shown in green. This is compared to a c-scan of a test interrupted at the same load level. Apart from a removed single element at $POD=0.72\text{mm}$ (point a in Figure 3) in the 45° ply (this element was removed for its large deformation to avert numerical collapse), there was no further fibre breakage development in the model until the catastrophic failure of the specimen. The non-linearity in the curve derives from the large scale delamination occurring. The final failure of the model was characterized by the pull-out of a block of 0° plies just ahead of the notch and surface 45° ply delamination. This failure mode is very similar as the experimental observation as shown in Figure 5. The predicted 0° ply pullout width is 8.7mm, which is slightly smaller than the experimental value of 11mm.

Figure 3 Load-POD curve of $[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_s$ (4mm) laminates

Figure 4 Comparison of predicted delamination with interrupted test C-scan result at load level 'Del' on figure 3

Figure 5 Comparison of experimental and predicted surface failure mode

2.Results of blocked ply $[0_4/90_4]_{2s}(4\text{mm})$ laminates

The Load vs. POD, delamination and surface failure of this lay-up are shown in Figure 6, 7 and 8. From the symmetry of this lay-up a quarter model could be used.

The delamination images taken at points marked "Del" in figure 6 were from very slightly different load levels due to the model not quite achieving the load level at which the test was interrupted. In this case the model image is taken from just prior to complete failure. Apart from a removed single element at $\text{POD}=2.92\text{mm}$ (point a in Figure 6) in the 2nd 0° ply (this element was removed for its large deformation to avert numerical collapse too), there is no further fibre breakage development in the model till the catastrophic failure of the specimen. The final failure of the model is

characterized by 0° ply pull-out and surface 0° ply peeling off. This failure mode is very similar to the experimental observation as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 6 Load-POD curves of $[0_4/90_4]_{2s}(4\text{mm})$ laminates

Figure 7 Comparison of predicted delamination with interrupted test C-scan result

Figure 8 Comparison of experimental and predicted surface failure mode

3. Results of blocked ply $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_s(2\text{mm})$ laminates

Load vs. POD, delamination and surface failure of this lay-up are shown in Figure 9, 10 and 11.

In the model of this lay-up, fibre breakage initiated in the -45° ply at a load level of 9.57 kN (point a in Figure 9). Its development into the 0° ply (point b), expansion in -45° ply (point c) and development into the 45° ply (point d) are marked on Figure 9. In experiments the initial failure of specimens occurred at the notch but no fibre failure was observed on the surface till the specimens finally failed by crushing at the back end, a mode which is not included in the model. The presence of tensile fibre failure at the notch in the experiment can not however be ruled out as the specimens have not been extensively interrogated for this. The delamination patterns compared in Figure 10 are in reasonable agreement but the numerical prediction is not as extensive as the experimental C-scan result. The visual appearance of the two failure modes is compared in Figure 11, and is very similar.

Figure 9 Load-POD curves of $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_s(2\text{mm})$ laminates

Figure 10 Comparison of predicted delamination with interrupted test C-scan result

Figure 11 Comparison of experimental and predicted surface failure mode

4. Results of blocked ply $[0_2/90_2]_{2s}(2\text{mm})$ laminates

In the experiments, specimens of this lay-up failed by a form of a global buckling at a load level of around 8kN. Models of this lay-up did not allow buckling due to the mid-plane symmetry constraint and only failed by fibre failure after the buckling load had been exceeded. Therefore the predicted results for this lay-up for final failure are not comparable with experimental results and only presented here as a reference in Figure 12. C-scan results showed that a large extent of delamination developed in the 0° ply direction before the buckling failure of the specimens. The model gave similar predictions at this load level, as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 12 Load-POD curves of $[0_2/90_2]_{2s}(2\text{mm})$ laminates

Figure 13 Comparison of predicted delamination with interrupted test C-scan result

5. Results of dispersed ply $[45/90-45/0]_{2s}(2\text{mm})$ laminates

In the model of this lay-up, fibre failure initiated in the 1st 0° ply (Figure 14, point a) but there was no significant load drop after this until the breakage developed into the 2nd 45° ply (point b) and -45° plies (point c). At points d and e the crack in the -45° ply extends beyond the region of the inserted intra ply cracks and unrealistically turns to follow the adjacent 0° ply splits. This load-POD curve is very similar to that of test no. 5. Both C-scan and model simulation showed that very limited delamination developed in this lay-up, as shown in Figure 15. There was extensive fibre failure inside the model but this failure did not propagate to the surface ply of the model. This is consistent with the experimental observation in Figure 16.

Figure 14 Load-POD curves of $[45/90-45/0]_{2s}(2\text{mm})$ laminates

Figure 15 Comparison of predicted delamination with interrupted test C-scan result

Figure 16 Comparison of experimental and predicted surface failure mode

6. Results of dispersed ply $[0/90]_{4s}(2\text{mm})$ laminates

The model failure of this lay-up initiated in the form of fibre breakage at point a in Figure 17. After point a, fibre breakage developed stably along the centerline of the specimen toward the back. The load in this process experienced a series of small jumps till the crack was close to the back edge (points b, c and d). This failure propagation mode is very similar as the experimental results, refer to the Load vs. POD curves in Figure 17 and surface failure in Figure 19. Delamination in this lay-up was limited to a small area around the notch tip, as shown in Figure 18.

Figure 17 Load-POD curves of $[0/90]_{4s}(2\text{mm})$ laminates

Figure 18 Comparison of predicted delamination with interrupted test C-scan result

Figure19 Comparison of experimental and predicted surface failure mode

7 Results of dispersed ply $[45/90-45/0]_{4s}(4\text{mm})$ laminates

In the model of this lay-up, fibre failure initiated in the 1st 0° ply at point a in Figure 20 but there was no significant load drop after this until the breakage developed into the 45° (point b) and -45° (point c) plies and extended further in -45° plies (point d). The load response of this lay-up is significantly different from the experimental result but the predicted fibre breakage initiation load level is very close to the experimental value, which suggests that a more significant number of failed elements rather than the single maximum stressed element should be removed after the Weibull criterion is satisfied. This would decrease the load bearing ability of the laminates after the fibre failure has initiated. The test data of this lay-up came from a pilot study which investigated a number of other testing parameters such as notch tip radius. Unfortunately only a single result was available for the 0.5mm radius notch and no C-scan data was available for this lay-up to compare with the model predicted delamination in Figure 21 and surface failure in Figure 22.

Figure 20 Load-POD curves of $[45/90-45/0]_{4s}(4\text{mm})$ laminates

Figure 21 Predicted (a) delamination and (b) surface failure

8. Results of dispersed ply $[0/90]_{8s}(4mm)$ laminates

The model failure of this lay-up initiated in the form of fibre breakage at point a in Figure 22. After the initiation, fibre breakage developed stably along the centerline of the specimen toward the back. The load in this process experienced a series of small jumps till the crack was close to the back. This failure propagation mode is very similar to the experimental results, refer to the Load vs. POD curves in Figure 22 and surface failure in Figure 24.. Delamination in this lay-up was limited to a small area around the notch tip, as shown in Figure 23.

Figure 22 Load-POD curves of $[0/90]_{8s}(4mm)$ laminates

Figure23 Comparison of predicted delamination with interrupted test C-scan result

Figure 24 Comparison of experimental and predicted surface failure mode

9.Summary of Predicted Failure Loads

The predicted failure loads for the different lay-ups are compared with the experimental results in the following Table 4 and Table 5. The 1st failure loads for $[45_4/90_4/45_4/0_4]_s$ and $[0_4/90_4]_{2s}$ lay-ups use the final catastrophic failure load since there is no fibre breakage. The 1st failure loads for the other 6 lay-ups adopted the load levels when the first fibre breakage initiated. In experiments the 1st failure loads were taken as values after which the loads dropped down by 5% or more. The maximum loads for all lay-ups took the maximum load values on Load vs. POD curves.

Table 4 Comparison of predicted 1st failure load and maximum failure load of dispersed plies in thickness direction with experimental results

Dispersed Plies in thickness direction						
Layup	Average load at 1 st significant load drop (kN)(CV,%)	Predicted 1 st Failure Load(kN)	Diff (%)	Average Maximum Load (kN)(CV,%)	Predicted Maximum Load(kN)	Diff (%)
[0/90] _{4s}	5.90(6.9)	6.26	+6.1	6.94(2.6)	7.11	+2.4
[0/90] _{8s}	11.64(6.5)	10.85	-6.8	11.64(6.5)	12.95	+11.2
[45/90/45/0] _{2s}	6.10(10.8)	6.08	-0.3	6.99(24.3)	8.38	+19.9
[45/90/45/0] _{4s}	9.23	8.36	-9.4	9.23	15.34	+66.2

 Fibre breakage

Table 5 Comparison of predicted 1st failure load and maximum failure load of blocked plies in thickness direction with experimental results

Blocked Plies in thickness direction						
Layup	Average load at 1 st significant load drop (kN) (CV,%)	Predicted 1 st Failure Load(KN)	Diff (%)	Average Maximum Load (kN) (CV,%)	Predicted Maximum Load(KN)	Diff (%)
[0 ₂ /90 ₂] _{2s}	7.94(10.7)	6.61	-16.8	9.12(3.0)	10.49	+15.0
[0 ₄ /90 ₄] _{2s}	20.74(0.5)	19.69	-5.1	20.74(0.5)	19.69	-5.1
[45 ₂ /90 ₂ /45 ₂ /0 ₂] _s	10.30(5.1)	9.57	-7.1	12.24(4.0)	10.80	-11.8
[45 ₄ /90 ₄ /45 ₄ /0 ₄] _s	17.41(0.2)	16.00	-8.1	17.41(0.2)	16.00	-8.1

 Fibre breakage

 pull-out failure

 Buckling failure

CONCLUSION

The method modelling delamination and splitting with cohesive elements and fibre failure using a global Weibull failure criterion gave very good results for most of the lay-ups in the OCT tests in four aspects: load vs. POD curves, surface failure appearance, delamination and fibre breakage. In the one exceptional case of the [45/90/45/0]_{4s} layup, the model could well predict the fibre failure initiation point but

gave much higher failure propagation loads than the experiment. This suggests that a cluster of elements rather than the single maximum stressed element might fail and need to be removed after the Weibull criterion is satisfied. A statistical fibre cluster failure criterion which could determine the size of the cluster needs to be developed for this purpose.

The models showed that splitting near the notch can effectively reduce the stress concentration around the notch and prevent fibre failure in the early stages of loading. Splits occur more easily in the blocked ply specimens due to the thicker ply blocks. These splits spread the stress concentration and form a much larger damage process zone. This explains the observation in the OCT tests that the blocked ply specimens tend to fail by delamination and have larger final failure loads. In dispersed ply specimens, splitting is prevented by greater constraint from neighbouring plies with different orientations, thus stress is less easily redistributed locally near the notch causing earlier fibre breakage and a more brittle failure.

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